

Functionalized Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles for the removal and remediation of Cr^{VI} metal ions from synthetic solutions

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Abstract : In the present study, polyethylene glycol coated iron-oxide beads were successfully used to adsorb Cr^{VI} from synthetic solutions. Studies on adsorption were carried out by varying parameters such as adsorbent dosage, pH, and contact time. 0.05 g of Fe₃O₄/PEG adsorbent showed highest adsorption capacity of 38 mg/g of adsorbent at pH 6 under 90 min of shaking time for 1000 ppm solution. Among the correlation coefficient values obtained using three different models (intra-particle diffusion model, pseudo-first order and kinetics), the pseudo-second order model proves to be the best fit with R² values of 0.9998.

Keywords : Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, polyethylene glycol, effluent treatment, metal ion adsorbents.

Introduction

Contamination of aqueous systems with heavy metals and their remediation has received increasing attention since the last decade due to growing environmental concerns. Toxic heavy metals like chromium, zinc, lead, copper and manganese present in industrial effluents are stable elements and cannot be digested by the water bodies and as result, they get passed up in the human food chain¹. Instead of biodegradation, the toxic heavy metals can get accumulated in humans and plants through ingestion of foods and drinking water.

Among the heavy metals considered as toxic pollutants when released into natural water bodies by industries related to textile, electroplating, leather tanning, etc., the impact of hexavalent chromium has received wider attention². In particular, wastewater from metal-processing industries generally contain alarmingly higher amount of Cr^{VI} released mainly during the rinsing of plated articles and from spent chromate passivation solutions. The untreated release of such industrial wastes without adequate treatment can pose a serious threat to general health as well as the environment³, and in particular, exposure to excessive amount of Cr^{VI} may cause diarrhea, dermati-

tis, hemorrhaging and cancer in the lungs⁴. According to USEPA, the permissible levels of Cr^{VI} ions in water is around 0.1 mg/L⁵, and for compliance within this limit, it is essential for the industries to reduce the amount of Cr^{VI} ions in their effluents to around the permissible level prior to discharging into public sewers. Among the different methods developed for extraction and removal of Cr^{VI} from industrial effluents, chemical redox method using Mg(OH)₂ followed by the precipitation of Cr^{VI} as its less toxic form, Cr^{III} is most widely used⁶. Compared to the conventional materials used until now, many researchers have now focused their attention on developing new materials having increased capacity, selectivity and affinity towards the target metals⁷. As an environmentally friendly alternative, microorganisms have also been used to accumulate heavy metals in addition to the use of bacterial and fungal "biomass" as biosorbents for the selective removal of radionuclides and heavy metals⁷.

Among the nanomaterials, ceramic metal oxide nanoparticles have been previously used for the recovery and remediation of heavy metals. However, these materials bind non-specifically, due to which their reversible recovery from the decontaminated water can be extremely

challenging⁸. Owing to their extremely smaller size but abundant surface reactive sites, the nanomaterials are highly reactive to heavy metals contaminants which inevitably change the behavior of the contaminants.

Magnetic nanoparticles are a class of nanoparticles consisting of magnetic elements such as nickel, cobalt, iron and their chemical compounds⁹. They have been the focus of much research recently because of their attractive properties such as high desorption capacity and easy separation¹⁰. The major limitation of naked nanoparticle sorbents is self agglomeration of the particles and thus reduced sorbent capacity. On the other hand, polyethylene glycol (PEG) is often used in drug delivery by modifying and stabilizing the drugs to improve selectivity and repel proteins, thus preventing proteins from denaturing the drugs. In the present study, we focus on the remediation of Cr^{VI} from synthetic solution using PEG modified magnetite nanoparticles, and testing its effectiveness of sorption under varying conditions such as pH, contact time and dosage.

Results and discussion

From the FTIR spectra of Fe₃O₄/PEG nanocomposite, the appearance of characteristic peaks at 3300, 1400, 1150 and 800 cm⁻¹ corresponding to O-H, C-C_{st}, C-H and C=O groups, respectively confirms the presence of PEG coating on magnetite surface. SEM micrographs as shown in Fig. 1 indicate the spherical morphology of Fe₃O₄/PEG nanocomposites with large surface area, which may aid in enhancing the adsorption of heavy metals from the industrial effluent.

Fig. 1. SEM micrographs of the synthesized Fe₃O₄/PEG nanocomposite at different magnifications : 5060x (left) and 11100x (right).

Fig. 2 shows the changes in specific adsorption (mg/g) as a function of (a) pH of adsorbate liquor solution; (b) adsorbent dosage and (c) adsorption time. The pH of the adsorbate liquor solution directly affects the extent of adsorption. This is due to the fact that pH is one of the major factors that determine the interaction between adsorbent and adsorbate. The PEG-Fe₃O₄ system was tested for the pH range of 3 to 6 of the chromium liquor and the efficiency of adsorption was found to increase with increasing pH. At pH 6, the highest adsorption capacity of 35 mg/g was achieved.

The sorption capacity of Fe₃O₄-PEG composites decrease with increasing dosage. The effect of dosage was tested for the range 0.05 to 0.2 g of the sorbent at pH 6 for 90 min contact time. Highest sorption capacity of 34.3 mg/g was attained with dosage of 0.05 g. For subsequent dosages, the graph showed a visible decline with lowest sorption capacity of 10.2 mg/g for 0.2 g of adsorbent.

The effect of contact time on adsorption was tested at pH 6 and for the dosage of 0.05 g. It was found that the sorption capacity increased steadily until 90 min to attain a maximum sorption capacity of 34 mg/g, beyond that time, the sorption process attained equilibrium due to the lack of active sites. This means that all the active sites were used up within the time span of 90 min under the given conditions.

Kinetics studies :

Freundlich and Langmuir adsorption isotherms are the most important and widely used isotherms to predict

Fig. 2. Changes in the specific adsorption (mg/g) as a function of (a) pH of adsorbate liquor solution; (b) adsorbent dosage (at pH 6 and 90 min of contact time) and (c) adsorption time (at pH 6 and 0.05 g dosage).

whether the adsorption process involved is a monolayer or multilayer processes. Out of the several kinetic models available to examine the controlling mechanism involved in the sorption kinetic process and to test the experimental data, the Lagrangian equation or pseudo-first order and second order equations were used for understanding the metal sorption kinetics of Fe₃O₄/PEG nanocomposite in our study. The correlation coefficients, 0.9981 and 0.9993 for Freundlich and Langmuir, respectively validate the theoretical and experimental studies. Comparing the maximum adsorption capacities obtained as a result of isotherm analysis (Langmuir : 12.81 mg/g and Freundlich : 2.57 mg/g), Langmuir adsorption isotherm fits best to the system under study. Among the correlation coefficient values obtained using three different models (intra-particle diffusion model, pseudo-first order and second order kinetics), the pseudo-second order model proves to be the best fit with R^2 values of 0.9998.

Experimental

Ferric chloride (FeCl₃), ferrous sulphate heptahydrate (FeSO₄.7H₂O), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and polyethylene glycol (PEG) were purchased from S.D. Fine Chemicals, India. The synthesis of Fe₃O₄-PEG nanocomposite beads were carried out as follows : 50 mL of 0.1 M FeCl₃ and 50 mL of 0.1 M FeSO₄.7H₂O were mixed in a beaker, and thoroughly stirred using a magnetic stirrer for 30 min. 50 ml of 0.8 M NaOH taken in a burette was added to the solution along with 10 ml of PEG under continuous stirring. The bead particles were allowed to settle down, filtered and washed with distilled water for many times. The beads were further dried in an air oven maintained at 100 °C for 12 h. The nanoparticles were

characterized using FTIR and SEM and used for further studies.

Cr^{VI} adsorption studies were carried out by changing the operational parameters such as adsorbent dosage, pH and contact time. In this study, the pH range was varied between 3 and 6, adsorption contact time varied from 30 to 180 min with an interval of 30 min and dosage altered from 0.05 to 0.2 g of the dry beads. The filtrates were analyzed for the residual Cr^{VI} in the solution using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Varian-AA240PS) at 340 nm. The amount of adsorption at time t , q_t (mg g⁻¹) was calculated by the relationship, $q_t = \frac{V*(C_0 - C_t)}{m}$ where ' C_0 and C_t ' are the concentrations of Cr^{VI} at initial time and at time t , respectively. ' V ' is the volume of aqueous solution and ' m ' is the mass of the adsorbent.

Conclusion

The iron-oxide nanoparticles were synthesized and modified with PEG using co-precipitation process. Fe₃O₄/PEG adsorbent showed highest adsorption capacity of 38 mg/g of adsorbent at pH 6, 0.05 g of adsorbent in 90 min for a 1000 ppm solution. This modification has the following advantages : (a) increase in number of active sites due to the presence of magnetite and PEG, (b) high specific surface area due to the presence of nanoparticles, (c) prevention of self-aggregation of nanoparticles which increases accessibility to active sites and (d) prevents oxidation of magnetite. This adsorption process fits best into Langmuir adsorption isotherm and follows pseudo-second order kinetic model, which shows that the adsorption is monolayer and both the adsorption isotherms indi-

cate favorable adsorption. Effectiveness of the adsorbent on actual industrial effluents containing high levels of Cr^{VI} and desorption of dichromate ions from the surface of the nanocomposite using chelating compounds like EDTA will be studied in the future.

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